

A new methodology to study and mitigate LoRaWAN and Sigfox coexistence issue

Domenico Garlisi, Antonino Pagano, Fabrizio Giuliano, Daniele Croce, Ilenia Tinnirello

University of Palermo, Italy

name.lastname@unipa.it

Abstract—According to IoT Analytics, NB-IoT, LoRaWAN, and Sigfox are today the most popular technologies for low-power wide-area networks (86% of the market), both in terms of end-user adoption as well as ecosystem support. While NB-IoT utilizes licensed bands, LoRaWAN and Sigfox both employ the sub-GHz ISM bands, potentially interfering with each other.

In this paper, we present a thorough coexistence study between LoRaWAN and Sigfox, in realistic urban scenarios, with different Duty Cycles and traffic conditions. The choice of such scenarios and simulation parameters are supported by an in-depth literature review. The results offer new insights on the coexistence of LoRaWAN and Sigfox for emerging IoT applications. Finally, we list possible interference mitigation strategies, and we analyze the performance obtained applying protection distance mechanisms.

Index Terms—Interference, SEAMCAT, LPWAN, IoT, ISM, LoRaWAN, LoRa, Sigfox, coexistence, CSS, UNB.

I. INTRODUCTION

The Internet of Things (IoT) is a global network of devices gathering information from systems and environments, and interacting with each other. In this field, Low-Power Wide-Area Network (LPWAN) technologies have emerged as a viable alternative to traditional wireless technologies to provide power-efficient and cost-effective wide area connectivity for the IoT. Indeed, the advantages of the LPWAN architectures include a wide coverage in the order of kilometers, and a low power consumption, with batteries lasting up to 10 years. According to IoT Analytics, the number of connected IoT devices is forecasted to grow from 7 billions in 2018 to 22 billions in 2025 [1]. Moreover, according to the same study, three LPWAN technologies, namely LoRaWAN [2], Sigfox [3], NB-IoT [4], are used to connect about 86% of the devices. While NB-IoT works in licensed bands, LoRaWAN and Sigfox share the same ISM bands. Since both technologies employ an Aloha access protocol, the proliferation of such devices can produce coexistence issues. On the other hand, LoRaWAN and Sigfox employ very different modulation schemes: while Sigfox utilizes an Ultra-Narrowband (UNB) 100 Hz signal and Binary Phase Shift Keying (BPSK) modulation, LoRaWAN exploits a 125-500 kHz Chirp Spread Spectrum (CSS) modulation. In the rest of the paper, we refer to LoRa/LoRaWAN as CSS and Sigfox as UNB and vice-versa. Given the different modulation employed, it is thus interesting to evaluate the coexistence of these technologies in realistic application scenarios, e.g. smart cities, industrial IoT, etc. Although some previous works have analyzed the interference among these technologies, e.g. [5], [6], these works either employ arbitrary simulation settings

or fail to provide insights on the achievable performance in large-scale scenarios. In contrast, the present work takes into account realistic node deployments, such as the ones in [7], considering variable node densities and traffic conditions, different deployments (e.g. indoor/outdoor, elevation, etc.), intra- and inter-technology interference, as well as possible interference mitigation strategies.

In particular, in this work we study the interference between the CSS and UNB systems in urban scenarios, focusing especially on the uplink which is the most critical. We employ accurate path-loss models and simulate realistic traffic scenarios (taken from a thorough literature review), considering node density distributions, Duty Cycle (DC) and modulation parameters typical of the considered technologies. We measure the interference probability, resulting from collisions of the same technology (self-interference), from the other technology (cross-interference), or both (mixed-interference) for CSS and UNB systems. Finally, analyze the performance obtained applying protection distance to the gateways, to mitigate the impact of interference. The experiments are conducted employing SEAMCAT [8], which is quite novel for IoT technology. This simulator is developed by CEPT/ECC and is widely adopted to analyze interference probability in large-scale scenarios. This tool provides fine-tunable settings, including several physical parameters (e.g. propagation model, node location, etc.), and evaluates the interference probability running Monte Carlo (MC) simulations. We offer the configuration files (including node density, DC and height distribution of the nodes) to the scientific community for repeatability and future integration of the research [9]. The main contributions of this paper are:

- 1) we study the path-loss models that best fit the considered technologies for urban scenarios (including both indoor and outdoor settings);
- 2) we configure SEAMCAT for realistic UNB and CSS deployments and offer all simulation files to the scientific community;
- 3) we analyze the interference probability in several traffic scenarios, showing the impact of self, cross and mixed interference for both configured systems;
- 4) we consider possible interference mitigation strategies, focusing on the performance obtained with protection distance mechanisms.

The remainder of the paper is organized as follows. A detailed analysis of the state of the art can be found in Sec. II. Sec. III, briefly presents the selected technologies and

their interference. Sec. IV recalls the SEAMCAT architecture and details the path-loss model employed. In Sec. V we describe the experiment scenarios and present the results of our simulations. Sec. VI discusses possible interference mitigation schemes and analyzes the performance obtained with protection distance. Finally, Sec. VII concludes the paper.

II. RELATED WORK

In this section, we report relevant literature studies regarding the coexistence of LoRa and Sigfox, as well as other related works employing SEAMCAT for interference studies.

A. Coexistence studies on Sigfox and LoRa

One of the first works evaluating the differences between CSS and UNB networks is [5], where both physical level and packet level performance are considered. The authors show that an UNB network has a larger coverage, while CSS-based networks are less sensitive to interference. Moreover, they analyze the case in which both technologies coexist and show that active rate and frequency management are fundamental for improving performance. Similarly, in [6] the impact of different types of ISM interference on LoRa modulation is evaluated and is demonstrated that narrowband interference suppression can significantly improve the resilience of LoRa. However, these works either employ unrealistic scenarios (i.e. with an arbitrary number of nodes and without considering indoor/outdoor settings), or fail to provide insights on the achievable performance in large-scale scenarios.

Authors in [10] experimentally evaluate the coexistence of LPWAN technologies in the ISM band. The results show a significant impact on the performance of LoRa and Sigfox from already installed IoT devices in smart homes, business parks, smart agriculture, etc. The work in [11] exploits a testbed setup to evaluate the impact of different sub-GHz technologies (Sigfox, Z-wave, and IO Home Control) on LoRa. Results show that there is a significant loss under Sigfox interference, especially when the interferer starts during the preamble and header time while loss is reduced if the interferer starts during the payload time. However, LoRa is only seen as the victim and the opposite is not considered. In [12] performance limits of LoRa have been discussed, and in [13] the impact of interference among LoRa nodes is analysed experimentally. However, these works do not consider the interference that LoRa and Sigfox might suffer when deployed in the same environments. Finally, [14] surveys the challenges of LPWANs and points out their design objectives and limits, analyzing coverage, energy efficiency, scalability, interference management, and quality of service. However, all these existing works do not consider interference in mixed high-density scenarios where multiple IoT technologies coexist in the same area and use the same ISM bands. Moreover, in this paper, we analyze the performance obtained with protection distance, as a possible interference mitigation mechanism.

B. SEAMCAT-based interference studies

The SEAMCAT simulator has been used in several previous works. For example, authors in [15] analyzed the interfer-

ence between Wi-Fi HaLow and Long Term Evolution (LTE) User Equipment (UE). The study employs both a theoretical method based on Minimum Coupling Loss and statistical MC simulations exploiting SEAMCAT. In [16] the authors studied interference of three industrial IoT technologies (WirelessHART, WiFi and Bluetooth) with a 5G uplink Macrocell. All simulation scenarios are composed of one victim technology, and one or more interfering systems in turn, with and without the presence of 5G uplink traffic. A coexistence work between LoRaWAN and SRDs is proposed in [17], where SEAMCAT is employed to measure the interference probability. In [18], [19] authors adopt the SEAMCAT Extended-Hata propagation model to analyze LoRa performance in urban scenarios and for coexistence between IEEE802.11ah and 802.15.4g, respectively. However, to the best of our knowledge, no previous work studied interference between Sigfox and LoRa technologies using SEAMCAT.

III. LPWAN TECHNOLOGIES AND THEIR INTERFERENCE

A typical LPWAN architecture comprises: i) IoT devices providing sensing, measurement, and/or control functionalities in a large geographic area; ii) wireless connection to a gateway (GW) or base station; and iii) a server or cloud platform, which processes, stores, and keeps available data for visualization and usage. To extend the communication range, often LPWAN technologies i) employ low frequency bands with favorable propagation characteristics, ii) apply modulation schemes which are robust to low SNR (Signal to Noise Ratio), iii) adopt simple MAC schemes to reduce power consumption. In LPWANs, communication is mostly device-initiated, meaning that an Up-Link (UL) message is transmitted when the device has some data to send. For the remainder of the time, the device is kept in sleep mode, while Down-Link (DL) traffic is generally permitted only after an UL transmission.

Among the different LPWANs, LoRaWAN is an open-source solution promoted by the LoRa Alliance. LoRaWAN uses Long Range (LoRa) modulation, patented by Semtech, based on CSS [2]. This technique encodes a set of bits into a single chirp. A chirp is a sinusoidal signal where the frequency is linearly increased or decreased in time over a fixed bandwidth. The Spreading Factor (SF) determines the duration of the chirps, and defines two modulation features: i) the time duration of each symbol; and ii) the number of raw bits encoded by that symbol, equal to SF. In LoRaWAN, the available Data Rates (DRs) are determined by the SF, bandwidth, and number of redundancy bits (Coding Rate). The bandwidth can be 125kHz, 250kHz or 500kHz (typically 125kHz is used in the 868MHz ISM band). Finally, LoRaWAN defines six different SFs (from SF7 to SF12), which result in different symbol times and almost orthogonal transmissions. The range can be extended in LoRaWAN by increasing the SF, thereby lowering the demodulation threshold. For example, with SF12 a signal with an SNR of -20 dB can be demodulated, while for SF7 a minimum SNR of -7.5 dB is required in order to receive the packet. Any time that a new packet is

Fig. 1. LoRaWAN and Sigfox channels overlapping in the 868MHz bands.

ready for transmission, devices attempt to transmit randomly selecting one of the available channels, as detailed later.

Sigfox is also a proprietary technology, where GWs and network servers are managed directly by Sigfox or other national operators authorized by Sigfox. Devices are certified by Sigfox before joining the network. In contrast to LoRaWAN, Sigfox uses a UNB modulation scheme: data is modulated by Differential Binary Phase Shift Keying (DBPSK) at 600 bps, generating a 100 Hz signal. The advantage of such a method is that the noise level present in a narrow-band communication channel is minimal. For redundancy, data is transmitted 3 times on different channels (to ensure frequency diversity) at different consecutive time intervals. There are 1920 channels available for the UL, and the same number for the DL. Moreover, together with time and frequency diversity, determined by the frequency hopping mechanism, Sigfox also uses spatial diversity since the network is designed so that every node is in the range of at least 3 different GWs [20].

As discussed previously, LoRaWAN and Sigfox both exploit the same ISM bands. In Europe, in particular, the band between 863 MHz and 870 MHz is allocated for license-free communications [21]. As depicted in Fig. 1, five LoRaWAN UL and DL channels are accommodated between 865.0 MHz and 868.0 MHz, while in the second sub-band (from 868.0 MHz to 868.6 MHz) are allocated 1920 Sigfox UL channels and 3 UL/DL LoRaWAN channels. In this band, about 200kHz are used by Sigfox ($1920 \times 100\text{Hz} = 192\text{kHz}$), completely overlapping the 125kHz LoRaWAN channel centered on 868.1 MHz. Both sub-bands 1 and 2 (see Fig. 1) are limited to 25mW (14dBm) transmission power and 1% DC (basically, this means 36s of Time of Air per hour). Sub-band 3 is interesting because the maximum transmission power is to 500mW with a 10% DC. While an end device would not be able to transmit such power running on batteries, a GW attached to the grid could use it for long range DL communications. Moreover, the larger DC allows the GW to communicate with many nodes. Nevertheless, LPWAN technologies are mainly employed for UL communications and the density of the GWs is usually less critical, so we omit this DL scenario in our analysis. Similar considerations can be done in other ISM bands, which we omit for the sake of brevity.

IV. THE SEAMCAT SIMULATOR AND PATH-LOSS TUNING

In our analysis, we employ SEAMCAT [8] (version 5.4.2), a complex statistical simulator based on the MC method, devised to assess the interference between different radio communication technologies. SEAMCAT is developed by CEPT/ECC

Working Group Spectrum Engineering (WGSE) within its sub-entity SEAMCAT Technical Group (STG). The simulator is based on the definition of a victim link, characterized by a transmitter and a receiver of a given technology, as well as one or more interfering links (including different technologies). For each technology, it is possible to specify several physical parameters of the node, including the propagation model, location (e.g. indoor/outdoor, height), antenna radiation diagram, transmission power (including emission mask), receiver blocking mask, etc., and any of these parameters can have a statistical distribution among nodes. The evaluation of the interference probability is performed by averaging the results of multiple simulated events. Indeed, following the statistical distributions of the physical parameters, for each event, the impact of interference is computed by comparing the signal strength of the victim link with the sum of the interfering signals, filtered by the transceiver power masks (including also adjacent channels). Thus, for each event the power received by the victim is computed taking into account both the transmissions power and the relative path-loss (PL), evaluated by considering the propagation model, and the environment parameters (e.g. position, height, etc.). An event is flagged as interfered (or good) when the Carrier to Interference ratio (C/I) value is lower (or higher) than a target threshold.

One of the main characteristics is thus related to the accurate computation of the PL. In the literature, several papers have dealt with real-world experiment campaigns for the estimation of the PL in LPWAN technologies. Table I reports a broad list of such studies, detailing the experiment location, the attenuation exponent η , and the PL0 received at the reference distance d_0 specified in the paper. The wall and floor attenuations are also described in indoor studies [22], [23], where internal walls attenuate about 4 dB and concrete walls up to 10-20 dB. To better compare the values, we also provide the PL at a common reference distance of 100m (last column in the table). We compared these values to the propagation model provided by SEAMCAT Extended Hata model (last row in the table). The difference between PL values extracted from SEAMCAT and the experimental ones is quite large: 23.56dB for the indoor case (114.49dB against 138.05dB, in average) and 20.61dB for the urban case (87.1dB versus 107.3dB). Therefore, to align SEAMCAT simulations to the real-world measurements, in our experiments we reduce the transmitted power accordingly.

V. SIMULATION SCENARIOS AND RESULTS

We designed accurate simulation scenarios taking into account important factors such as the propagation environments, node density and transmission DC, elevation of the antennas, etc. In particular, we exploited the realistic distributions described in the ETSI Technical Report 103 526 [7], with a statistical distribution of the device elevation of 1.5, 9, and 30 meters. Furthermore, we consider the urban scenario with 90% of the devices placed indoor and the remaining 10% deployed in an outdoor environment. Regarding the network density, we define a base scenario with 1000 devices/km², following [32], and we vary the receiver signal strength (RSS) of the

TABLE I
PATH-LOSS COMPARISON FOR SIGFOX AND LORA TECHNOLOGIES IN URBAN SCENARIOS

Ref.	Technology	Location	Scenario	Ref. dist. (d0) [m]	PL(d0) [dB]	η	PL(100m) [dB]
[22]	LoRa	4 types of buildings	indoor	1	36.5	4	140.4
[23]	LoRa	Lancaster, UK	indoor	40	127.41	2.08	135.7
[8]	LoRa/SigFox	SEAMCAT, Extended Hata	indoor	-	-	-	114.5
[24]	LoRa	Beirut, Lebanon	outdoor	1000	140.7	3.12	109.5
[25]	LoRa	Oulu, Finland	outdoor	1000	128.95	2.32	105.8
[26]	LoRa	Dortmund, Germany	outdoor	1000	132.25	2.65	105.8
[27]	LoRa	Delft, The Netherlands	outdoor	1	23.9	3.89	101.7
[28]	LoRa	Dakar peninsula, Senegal	outdoor	1000	133.6	2.8	105.6
[29]	Sigfox	Brno, Czech Republic	outdoor	100	118.04	3.76	118.0
[30]	Sigfox	Prague, Czech Republic	outdoor	1000	121	1.68	104.2
[31]	Sigfox	Belfast, UK	outdoor	1000	139.8	3.2	107.8
[8]	LoRa/Sigfox	SEAMCAT, Extended Hata	outdoor	-	-	-	87.1

TABLE II
CONFIGURATION DC OF THE EXPERIMENT SCENARIOS

	ToA (12 Bytes) [sec]	Equal DC (1%)			Equal data rate		
		#pkt/day	ToA/day [sec]	DC [%]	#pkt/day	ToA/day [sec]	DC [%]
SF7	0.063	13714	863.94	1.0	144	9.07	0.0105
SF10	0.410	2107	863.91	1.0	144	59.04	0.068
UNB	6.0	144	864.00	1.0	144	864.00	1.0

TABLE III
SIGFOX AND LORAWAN SEAMCAT SYSTEMS PARAMETERS

Parameters	UNB device		UNB GW		CSS device		CSS GW	
TX PW(dBm EIRP)	16.25	29.25	16.25	29.25	16.25	29.25	16.25	29.25
Ant. Gain(dBi omni)	0	5.15	0	5.15	0	5.15	0	5.15
TX BW(Hz)	250	1K	250	1K	125K	125K	125K	125K
Power Control	N/A	N/A	Enabled	Enabled	Enabled	Enabled	Enabled	Enabled
SF	-	-	7	10	7	10	7	10
RX NF (dB)	8	7	7	7	7	7	7	7
Req. SINR (dB)	7	7	-8	-16.3	-8	-16.3	-8	-21.9
Sensitivity (dBm)	-124	-136	-124	-132	-124	-132	-124	-137

victim technology from -130dBm to -80dBm. For the CSS network, we considered a setup with a distribution of different SFs, following ETSI TR 103 526 (Fig. 6) [7] and CEPT-SE24 [32], which describe the percentage of adopted SFs per number of gateways. Moreover, we exploited the results obtained in [17] to define a scenario with an average number of gateways equal to 0.5/Km². Since the LoRaWAN standard also includes the Adaptive Data Rate (ADR) algorithm which dynamically changes the SFs of the nodes, for CSS simulations we divided nodes in predefined groups each using a specific SF. In particular, unless specified otherwise, we use 65% of the devices working at SF7 and 35% at SF10. Indeed, according to the above studies, SF7 is the most significantly used, while SF10 has a Time on Air (ToA) consumption per day that is close to the weighted average of the ToA for all SFs from 8 to 12. Finally, regarding the UNB network, no particular tuning is required apart from the node distribution, assumed uniform.

We consider two different load conditions: in the first (called *Equal DC*) both UNB and CSS are configured to transmit at maximum DC (1%). In this case, the data transmitted by CSS is greater than UNB: assuming a payload size of 12 bytes, 13,714 and 2,107 packets/day are sent using SF7 and SF10 respectively, compared to 144 UNB. In the second case (called

Fig. 2. Self-interference probability results for UNB and CSS networks in the equal DC (a) or equal data rate (b) scenarios.

Equal data rate) both networks transmit 144 packets/day, corresponding to a DC of 0.0105%, 0.068% and 1% for CSS SF7, CSS SF10 and UNB respectively. These configurations are summarized in Table II, while other parameters specific to UNB and CSS devices are reported in Table III. Finally, in our simulation campaigns we consider the following scenarios: (i) *Self-interference*, when only one system is deployed; (ii) *Cross-interference*, evaluating the interference on a victim technology by a different one; (iii) *Mixed-interference*, when both self- and cross-interference are present.

A. Self-interference scenario

Fig. 2, shows the simulation results for the self-interference scenario, in the two load conditions discussed previously. In particular, Fig. 2(a) shows the results when the networks are loaded with equal DC, i.e. when nodes transmit with the maximum DC of 1%. The blue curve (circular marker) represents the self-interference probability for UNB technology, which is 21.6% in the worst case, when the received power of the victim is lowest. The other curves describe the CSS self-interference for three different SFs, namely SF7 (asterisks), SF10 (diamonds) and SF12 (triangles). Since, according to [7] (Table 10), the sensitivity of SF7 is -124dBm, we do not evaluate the interference probability for RSS of -130dBm, as no packet can be received with RSS lower than -124dBm. From the figure, the self-interference of CSS shows

Fig. 3. Cross-interference probability for the equal DC scenario for the UNB system (a), and CSS systems (b).

an interference probability about 20% higher compared to UNB. This difference depends on the modulation scheme and bandwidth efficiency (data rate divided by the bandwidth per hertz), whereas UNB is more robust than CSS modulation but also has lower bandwidth efficiency. Indeed, Fig. 2(b) shows the results in case of the equal data rate scenario, with a traffic load of 144 packets/day, and in this case, CSS experiences a significantly reduced self-interference probability compared to UNB. In particular, the results show that the self-interference of the CSS systems is around one order of magnitude lower than UNB, due to the much lower ToA of the CSS packets.

B. Cross-interference scenario

Fig. 3 describes the probability of cross-interference between CSS and UNB, as a function of the victim's RSS, in the equal DC condition which is the most challenging in terms of coexistence. In particular, Fig. 3(a) shows the interference probability for UNB as the victim when interfered by CSS, and in the worst scenario, i.e. with -130 dBm RSS for the victim, the interference probability is 36%. Vice-versa, Fig. 3(b) shows the cross-interference results when CSS represents the victim. In this case, we tested three different SFs independently (namely, SF7, SF10, SF12), and both SF10 and SF12 are more robust than UNB (in the worst-case scenario of -130 dBm RSS), with the interference probability equal to 30.3% and 21% respectively. Instead, SF7 is less robust to interference, with 27.1% interference probability against 15.1% of UNB (measured at -120 dBm of RSS).

C. Mixed-interference scenario

Fig. 4 shows the simulation results in the mixed scenario. In this case, the interfering nodes are equally distributed among UNB and CSS (i.e. 50% of the nodes using UNB and 50% using CSS). For the equal DC experiment, Fig. 4(a) shows an interference probability for UNB very close to CSS at SF12, while the other SFs are more sensitive to interference. Finally, in case of equal data rate, Fig. 4(b) shows a lower interference probability for all systems, especially for UNB (due to the lower ToA consumed by LoRa in this experiment). Moreover, compared to cross-interference, the mixed scenario has less impact on UNB (e.g for RSS=-130dBm the interference probability is 6.5% less), while CSS is affected

Fig. 4. Mixed-interference for the equal DC (a) or equal data rate (b) scenario.

negatively (e.g. SF12 loses about 10% at -130dBm). However, if we consider performance in terms of average throughput, the result is opposite: in the worst-case scenario, UNB delivers only 101 packets/day, against 403 pkt/day, 1177 pkt/day and 8270 pkt/day for CSS with SF12, SF10, and SF7 respectively.

VI. DISCUSSION AND POSSIBLE SOLUTIONS

The presented results highlight the importance of mitigating the interference caused by heterogeneous technologies sharing the same frequency bands. As discussed in [14], possible solutions are: (i) cognitive radios, to exploit opportunistic channel access techniques; (ii) protection distance, arranging devices at a distance that significantly reduces the probability of interference; (iii) smart antennas, to direct power only in the areas where devices are most concentrated and finally (iv) multiple gateways, to reduce the transmit power and consequently lower interference. All these solutions can be analyzed using SEAMCAT. As an example, we present here the results obtained exploiting protection distance: we run two different experiments in the mixed scenario with Equal DC by considering a protection distance of 0, 500 and 1000 meters. Moreover, we defined three different levels of victim's RSS: -120 dBm (worst case), -110 dBm (typical) and -100 dBm (best case). In Fig. 5(a), we observe that for UNB a protection distance of 500 m reduces the probability of interference, in the worst case of -120 dBm, from 12% to 6% (thus a 50% reduction) compared to no protection distance. The improvement obtained using a protection distance of 1 Km is an additional 33% reduction in interference probability. Fig. 5(b) shows the results of the experiments when the victim is CSS. In this case the probability of interference decreases from 14% to 7% with protection distance of 500m and victim RSS equal to -120 dBm, again obtaining a decrease of 50%. For higher RSS the interference is still higher than UNB but nevertheless below 5% and 2% at lowest.

VII. CONCLUSION

In this work, we presented a coexistence study of CSS and UNB technologies, in realistic deployment scenarios and traffic conditions. The environment and system parameters are supported by an in-depth literature review in order to build accurate LPWAN simulation scenarios in terms of node

Fig. 5. Protection distance effects in mixed-interference scenario with DC=1% and density of 1000 nodes/Km² for UNB (a) and CSS (b) victims.

density, DC, indoor/outdoor locations, antenna elevation, etc. The experimental evaluations are executed using the SEAMCAT simulator and the configuration files are made available to the scientific community to enable future integration of the research. Results have demonstrated that, if the RSS is high enough (e.g. above -90dBm), UNB and CSS systems may coexist safely. However, in more extreme conditions (e.g. at the cell edge), UNB is more robust to interference, although CSS generally offers higher throughputs. Finally, we consider possible interference mitigation strategies, showing the performance obtained using protection distance. Overall, this study represents an important analysis and risk assessment for future IoT scenarios where both LPWANs might coexist.

ACKNOWLEDGMENT

This work was supported in part by the EU H2020 project ELEGANT (Grant agreement ID: 957286), by the Italian research programs PON FSE-FESR Ricerca e Innovazione 2014-2020, DOT1420214, and PO FESR Sicilia 2014-2020 project SAWE (Support, Alerting, Early Warning), n. 08PA9511000101.

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